

Effect of hollow inclusion-matrix debonding on the elastic properties of particulate composites

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SUMMARY

This work aims at understanding the effect of particle-matrix interfacial debonding on the elastic properties of hollow-particle filled composites. A series solution based on the Gakerkin method is derived for a hollow-inclusion embedded in an infinite matrix at various debonding levels. The results show stress intensification at particle-matrix interface along with a remarkable dependence of the composite stiffness on the debonding extent.

Keywords: Debonding, particulate composites, syntactic foams, marine composites, elastic properties.

INTRODUCTION

Naturally buoyant materials are of great interest for marine structural applications. Syntactic foams, composed of hollow particles (microballoons) embedded in a matrix material, are among the promising materials for such applications due to their low density, low moisture absorption, and the possibility to tailor their mechanical properties over a wide range [1]. Glass hollow-particle fillers and vinyl ester resin matrix are used in marine applications [2]. Unlike open-cell foams where porosity is interconnected and any damage to the material can lead to significant amount of absorbed moisture, syntactic foams have porosity enclosed inside hollow particles and damage to the material does not lead to enhanced moisture absorption [3]. In addition, published studies have shown that the elastic modulus of syntactic foams can be higher and the density can be lower than that of the matrix material, which leads to significantly higher specific modulus in syntactic foams [4].

The buoyancy aid applications of syntactic foams require high volume fraction of inclusions in the matrix to obtain the maximum density reduction. While experimental studies on high inclusion volume fraction syntactic foams are readily available for a variety of loading conditions, corresponding modeling efforts are lacking. Most of the available models use dilute dispersion approaches to estimate the effective elastic properties of syntactic foams [5-6]. In our previous work we have successfully used the differential scheme proposed in [7] to predict the effective elastic modulus of syntactic foams based on the modulus and volume fractions of glass, the material of microballoons, and vinyl ester, the matrix material [4]. Use of differential scheme allows using the model up to the particle packing limit in the composite. In addition, the

existing modeling efforts consider perfect interfacial bonding between the particle and the matrix material. However, such assumption has been shown to be generally incorrect for glass microballoon/vinyl ester syntactic foams, see Figure 1a. In [8], we showed that interfacial debonding is largely responsible for syntactic foam failure under flexural loading.

The present study is focused on evaluating the effect of inclusion-matrix interfacial debonding on the effective elastic properties and failure behavior of syntactic foams. In particular, the present study addresses the problem of uniaxial tensile loading of a hollow inclusion embedded in a matrix material in presence of various levels of preexisting debonding. The displacement and stress fields in the system are represented using solid spherical harmonics. By imposing the boundary and interfacial conditions, the problem is reduced to a single integral equation in terms of the normal interfacial stress. The integral equation is solved by using a highly-computationally efficient version of the Galerkin method, in which a special function is included in the basis set to grasp the singular behaviour of the stress at the debond tip. The method is applied to the analysis of the interfacial stress, the effective Young's modulus of the composite, and the strain energy release rate. The derived results are validated by direct comparison with extensive finite element simulations.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The representative volume element (RVE) analyzed in this work comprises a hollow spherical inclusion embedded in an infinitely extended matrix. The geometry of the studied RVE along with the selected spherical coordinate system is presented in Figure 1b. Here, r is the radial coordinate, θ is the zenith angle, and φ is the azimuth angle. The matrix of the RVE is uniaxially loaded in the y -direction by a remotely applied stress σ_∞ . The geometry of the hollow inclusion is described by the outer radius a and the radius ratio η that is defined as the ratio between the inner and the outer radii.

The materials of the two bodies are assumed to be homogenous and isotropic. The Lamé's constants of the materials are denoted by λ_m and μ_m and λ_i and μ_i for the matrix and the inclusion respectively. Similarly, the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the materials are referred to as $E_{m,i}$ and $\nu_{m,i}$. Due to the problem symmetry, it is assumed that the interface between the inclusion and the matrix material fails along two spherical caps located at the inclusion poles. The extent of debonding is quantified by the angle θ_0 as shown in Figure 1b, that is, the matrix-inclusion debonding is localized in the regions $0 \leq \varphi \leq 2\pi$ and $0 \leq \theta \leq \theta_0$ and $\pi - \theta_0 \leq \theta \leq \pi$. In addition, it is assumed that the interface is

Figure 1 (a). Micrograph of a syntactic foam fractured under flexural loading conditions showing significant interfacial debonding and (b) representative volume element.

capable of exclusively transferring normal load, that is, the shear stress at the interface is set to zero. Consistently with the cylindrical symmetry with respect to the y -direction, the component of the displacement along the azimuthal coordinate is zero, the components of the displacement along the radial and zenith coordinate are independent of φ , and the solution is symmetric with respect to the xz -plane. Thus, the three-dimensional problem is reduced to a two-dimensional problem and only the region $\theta_0 \leq \theta \leq \pi/2$ is analyzed.

Using the superposition principle, the solution of the problem under investigation is divided into simpler subproblems as suggested in [9] and sketched in Figure 2:

- I. matrix with a spherical void of radius a under uniaxial tensile loading condition;
- II. matrix with a spherical void of radius a loaded by an unknown normal traction distribution $\sigma(\theta)$ in the void, such that $\sigma(\theta) = \sigma(\pi - \theta)$ and $\sigma(\theta) = 0$ for $0 \leq \theta \leq \theta_0$;
- III. hollow-inclusion loaded by $-\sigma(\theta)$ at its outer surface.

Figure 2. Mechanical equivalence of the original problem and the divided subproblems.

The displacement and stress fields for each of these problems presented can be written in terms of the series solution outlined in the Appendix. In what follows, the notation is consistent with equations (A1) and (A2) in the Appendix and superscripts (I), (II), and (III) are used to identify the solutions of each problem. The traction field $\sigma(\theta)$ is determined by imposing the radial displacement continuity across the intact interface, that is, by imposing

$$u_r^{(I)}(a, \theta) + u_r^{(II)}(a, \theta) - u_r^{(III)}(a, \theta) = 0 \quad (1)$$

in the interval $[\theta_0, \pi/2]$.

Problem I

The remote stress can be written in spherical coordinates as

$$\bar{\sigma}_{rr} = \frac{\sigma_\infty}{3} [1 + 2P_2(\cos \theta)] \quad \bar{\tau}_{r\theta} = \frac{\sigma_\infty}{3} \frac{dP_2(\cos \theta)}{d\theta} \quad (2)$$

The solution in the matrix can be written in the form of equation (A2), where the elastic constants are specified for the matrix material, and the constants A_n , B_n , C_n , and D_n are determined by setting

$$\sigma_{rr}^{(I)} \Big|_{r=a} = \tau_{r\theta}^{(I)} \Big|_{r=a} = 0 \quad \sigma_{rr}^{(I)} \Big|_{r \rightarrow \infty} = \bar{\sigma}_{rr} \quad \tau_{r\theta}^{(I)} \Big|_{r \rightarrow \infty} = \bar{\tau}_{r\theta} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the non-vanishing constants in equation (2) are

$$A_0 = -\frac{\sigma_\infty}{12\mu_m(1+\nu_m)} \quad B_2 = \frac{\sigma_\infty}{6\mu_m} \quad C_2 = \frac{5a^3\sigma_\infty}{12\mu_m(7-5\nu_m)} \quad (4)$$

$$D_0 = -\frac{a^3\sigma_\infty}{12\mu_m} \quad D_2 = \frac{a^5\sigma_\infty}{2\mu_m(7-5\nu_m)}$$

In addition,

$$\frac{2\mu_m}{a\sigma_\infty} u_r^{(I)}(a, \theta) = \frac{3(\nu_m - 1)[4 + 5(\nu_m + 1)\cos 2\theta]}{2(5\nu_m^2 - 2\nu_m - 7)} \quad (5)$$

Problem II

In this section, the deformations of the matrix due to the normal stress $\sigma(\theta)$ are analyzed. The function $\sigma(\theta)$ can be conveniently written in terms of solid harmonics as

$$\sigma(\theta) = \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^{\infty} \sigma_n P_n(\cos \theta) \quad (6)$$

where the coefficient σ_n can be expressed as

$$\sigma_n = (2n+1) \int_{\theta_0}^{\pi} \sigma(\theta) P_n(\cos \theta) d \cos \theta \quad (7)$$

due to the orthogonality of the even Legendre's polynomials and the fact that $\sigma(\theta)$ is zero for $0 \leq \theta \leq \theta_0$. The solution in the inclusion can be written in the form of equation (A2), where the elastic constants are specified for the matrix material, and the constants A_n , B_n , C_n , and D_n are determined by setting

$$\sigma_{rr}^{(II)} \Big|_{r=a} = \sigma(\theta) \quad \tau_{r\theta}^{(II)} \Big|_{r=a} = 0 \quad \sigma_{rr}^{(II)} \Big|_{r \rightarrow \infty} = \tau_{r\theta}^{(II)} \Big|_{r \rightarrow \infty} = 0 \quad (8)$$

Therefore, $A_n = B_n = 0$, and C_n and D_n are given by

$$C_n = \frac{-a^{n+1}\sigma_n}{4\mu_m[n^2 + (1-2\nu_m)n + 1 - \nu_m]} \quad D_n = \frac{-a^{n+3}\sigma_n(n^2 - 2 + 2\nu_m)}{4\mu_m(n+2)[n^2 + (1-2\nu_m)n + 1 - \nu_m]} \quad (9)$$

By substituting equation set (9) in equation (A2) one obtains

$$\frac{2\mu_m}{a\sigma_\infty} u_r^{(2)}(a, \theta) = - \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+1)[2(1-\nu_m)n^2 + (4-5\nu_m)n + 1 - \nu_m]}{(n+2)[n^2 + (1-2\nu_m)n + 1 - \nu_m]} P_n(\cos \theta) \times$$

$$\times \int_{\theta_0}^{\pi} \frac{\sigma(\hat{\theta})}{\sigma_\infty} P_n(\cos \hat{\theta}) \sin \hat{\theta} d\hat{\theta} \quad (10)$$

Problem III

In this section, the deformations of the inclusion due to the normal stress $-\sigma(\theta)$ are analyzed. The boundary conditions for this problem are

$$\sigma_{rr}^{(III)} \Big|_{r=a\eta} = \tau_{r\theta}^{(III)} \Big|_{r=a\eta} = 0 \quad \sigma_{rr}^{(III)} \Big|_{r=a} = \sigma(\theta) \quad \tau_{r\theta}^{(III)} \Big|_{r=a} = 0 \quad (11)$$

The expression for the coefficients in the series solution is not reported here for brevity. Only the displacement at the inclusion outer radius is presented

$$\frac{2\mu_m}{a\sigma_\infty} u_r^{(3)}(a, \theta) = \beta \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+1)N(n, \eta, \nu_i)}{D(n, \eta, \nu_i)} P_n(\cos \theta) \int_{\theta_0}^{\pi} \frac{\sigma(\hat{\theta})}{\sigma_\infty} P_n(\cos \hat{\theta}) \sin \hat{\theta} d\hat{\theta} \quad (12)$$

Here, $\beta = \mu_m/\mu_i$ and the functions $N(n, \eta, \nu_i)$ and $D(n, \eta, \nu_i)$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned} N = & -4\eta(-2-3n+n^2+5n^3+6n^4+2n^5) - (1+2n)^2(8-10n-7n^2+6n^3+3n^4)\eta^{2n} \\ & + 2n(6-5n-18n^2+n^3+12n^4+4n^5)\eta^{2+2n} + (1+2n)^2(4-2n-n^2+2n^3+n^4)\eta^{4+2n} \\ & + 4(-1-4n-2n^2+n^3+4n^4+2n^5)\eta^{3+4n} - 4\nu_i(-2+n+n^2) \\ & \times [-(1+n)^2(3+2n)\eta - (1+2n)^2(-3+n+n^2)\eta^{2n} + n^2(-1+2n)\eta^{3+4n} \\ & + n(-3+n+8n^2+4n^3)\eta^{2+2n}] - 4(1+2n)\nu_i^2 [(-4-4n+3n^2+2n^3)\eta + (1+2n)\eta^{4+2n} \\ & + (4+6n-6n^2-4n^3)\eta^{2n} + (-1-4n+3n^2+2n^3)\eta^{3+4n}] \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} D = & (2+n+n^2)[-4(1+n+n^2)^2\eta + (1+2n)^2(4-2n-n^2+2n^3+n^4)\eta^{2n} - \\ & - 2n(6-5n-18n^2+n^3+12n^4+4n^5)\eta^{2+2n} + (1+2n)^2(4-2n-n^2+2n^3+n^4)\eta^{4+2n} - \\ & - 4(1+n+n^2)^2\eta^{3+4n} + 4(1+2n)^2\nu_i^2(\eta - \eta^{2n} - \eta^{4+2n} + \eta^{3+4n})] \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

GOVERNING INTEGRAL EQUATION AND NUMERICAL SOLUTION

The stress distribution and deformations of the RVE are obtained by summing the general solutions of the above illustrated problems and imposing the displacement continuity across the intact interface, see equation (1). By applying this procedure, the following homogeneous Fredholm integral equation of the first kind is obtained

$$\int_{\theta_0}^{\pi} F(\theta, \hat{\theta}) \hat{\sigma}(\hat{\theta}) d\hat{\theta} = -\frac{2\mu_m}{a\sigma_\infty} u_r^{(1)}(a, \theta) \quad (15)$$

where $\hat{\sigma}(\hat{\theta}) = \sigma(\hat{\theta})/\sigma_\infty$ is the relative radial stress field at the interface, and $F(\theta, \hat{\theta})$ is the Fredholm kernel given by

$$F(\theta, \hat{\theta}) = \sin \hat{\theta} \left\{ \begin{aligned} & - \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+1)[2(1-\nu_m)n^2 + (4-5\nu_m)n + 1 - \nu_m]}{(n+2)[n^2 + (1-2\nu_m)n + 1 - \nu_m]} P_n(\cos \theta) P_n(\cos \hat{\theta}) \\ & - \beta \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+1)N(n, \eta, \nu_i)}{D(n, \eta, \nu_i)} P_n(\cos \theta) P_n(\cos \hat{\theta}) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (16)$$

Since the kernel is expressed as an infinite summation, equation (15) represents a Fredholm degenerate integral equation. The numerical solution of this equation is approximated by truncating the kernel at the first nonzero M terms. The technique used to solve equation (15) is based on the Galerkin method. The stress field is expanded as a linear combination of independent basis functions and the coefficients of the expansion are determined by projecting the integral equation onto the basis set, see for example [10-11]. More specifically, the stress field is expressed as

$$\hat{\sigma}(\hat{\theta}) = \sum_{n=0}^d c_n \varphi_n(\hat{\theta}) \quad (17)$$

where c_n is the n -th unknown coefficient, φ_n the n -th basis functions, and $d+1$ is the total number of basis functions used for the approximation. The coefficients c_n 's are determined by solving the following set of $d+1$ linear equations

$$\sum_{n=0}^d c_n \int_{\theta_0}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \int_{\theta_0}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} F(\theta, \hat{\theta}) \varphi_n(\hat{\theta}) \varphi_r(\theta) d\hat{\theta} = - \int_{\theta_0}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{2\mu_m}{a\sigma_\infty} u_r^{(l)}(a, \theta) \varphi_r(\theta) d\theta \quad (18)$$

In this study, the basis function set is selected to be the set of the first d even Legendre polynomials $\{P_n(\cos\theta) | n = 0, 2, \dots, 2d - 2\}$ enriched by a special function φ_0 that grasps the singular behavior of the radial stress distribution in the proximity of the debond tip. The special function φ_0 depends on the mismatch between the elastic constants of the matrix and inclusion materials as well as the extent of debonding, see for example [12-16]. According to [16], the singularity function can be expressed as follows:

$$\varphi_0(\theta) = \sin \left[\gamma \log \left(\sin \frac{\theta}{2} - \sin \frac{\theta_0}{2} \right) \right] / \left(\sin \frac{\theta}{2} - \sin \frac{\theta_0}{2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (19)$$

where γ is a constant that depends on the constituents' properties and is given by

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{2\pi} \log \left(\frac{3\beta + 1 - 4\beta\nu_i}{3 + \beta - 4\nu_m} \right) \quad (20)$$

In this study, the material properties are 0.2 for β , 0.2 for ν_i , and 0.3 for ν_m . Further, numerical experiments for these parameters show that a fully converged solution is obtained by selecting $M=51$ and $d=3$. The integrals in equation (18) are analytically computed in case they involve basis functions from the set of Legendre polynomials, while integrals involving the special function are evaluated numerically. Once the coefficients c_n are determined, the displacement in the RVE is found by calculating the coefficients in equation (7) and replacing in the series solutions in the Appendix. Note that the solution for the solid inclusion is obtained by setting $\eta \rightarrow 0$ in equation (15).

EFFECTIVE YOUNG'S MODULUS

The effective Young's modulus of the composite is computed by equating the elastic energy stored in the RVE with the elastic energy stored in an isotropic homogenous medium of Young's modulus E_{eff} of the same dimensions under uniaxial loading. In particular, the elastic energy stored in the RVE is decomposed as [17]

$$U = U^0 + U_{INT} \quad (21)$$

where U^0 is the energy stored in the RVE in case the inclusion is replaced with matrix material and U_{INT} is the interaction energy between the matrix and inclusion. The energies U and U^0 are given by

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \frac{4\pi a^3 \sigma_\infty^2}{6\mu_m (1 + \nu_m) \Phi} \quad U^0 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{4\pi a^3 \sigma_\infty^2}{3E_{eff} \Phi} \quad (22)$$

where Φ is the volume fraction of the inclusion in the RVE. Using the Eshelby's formula [17] and accounting for the problem symmetries, U_{INT} be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
U_{INT} = & 2\pi \int_0^{\pi/2} \sigma_{rr}^0(a, \theta) u_r(a, \theta) + \tau_{r\theta}^0(a, \theta) u_\theta(a, \theta) a^2 \sin \theta d\theta \\
& - 2\pi \int_0^{\pi/2} \sigma_{rr}(a, \theta) u_\theta^0(a, \theta) + \tau_{r\theta}(a, \theta) u_\theta^0(a, \theta) a^2 \sin \theta d\theta
\end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

where the superscript zero refers to the uniaxial loading of the body composed of the matrix material. By substituting for the displacement and stress distributions the solution of the Galerkin procedure in (23), equation (21) can be solved for the effective Young's modulus. Moreover, the energy release rate is computed from equation (21), as the derivative of the elastic strain energy with respect to the total debonded surface.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Theoretical results are validated by finite element analysis (FEA) results obtained using a commercial code ANSYS 11.0. The model consists of a spherical inclusion in a cylindrical domain and is reduced to a two-dimensional model using axisymmetry. The cylindrical domain is selected for conveniently applying boundary conditions in the model. PLANE82 element is selected for meshing both the inclusion and the surrounding matrix. The particle volume fraction is 0.067 in order to approximate the case of an infinitely dilute dispersion of inclusions. The particle-matrix interfacial bonding is defined by using TARGE169 and CONTA175 elements. The interface is defined to be frictionless and the contact pairs' parameters are tuned to avoid inclusion-matrix penetration. The effective Young's modulus is computed by calculating the work done by the traction field applied at the cylinder boundary and equating it with the energy stored in a homogenous and isotropic cylinder.

RESULTS

Figure 3 displays the interfacial normal stress for a solid and a hollow inclusion composite computed using FEA and the proposed method. FEA results are in very good agreement with numerical results based on the Galerkin method, despite the fact that the Galerkin method utilizes an extremely condensed set of basis functions. Figure 3 shows that the radial stress at the interface is tensile until θ reaches approximately 70° . This suggests that debonding levels higher than 70° would not further deteriorate the composite properties. In other words, a completely failed interface would still be able to carry compressive load in the equatorial region of the inclusion.

Figure 3. Radial stress at the interface for (a) solid and (b) hollow inclusion ($\eta=0.5$).

Figure 4a illustrates the relative change in the composite effective Young's modulus per unit inclusion volume fraction for different values of θ_0 and η . Figure 4a reports also the analytical solution for the case of fully bonded particle and the case of a spherical cavity in the matrix material. The former solution is derived by substituting $\theta_0=0$ in the problem set outlined above whereas the latter solution stems directly from Problem I. In general, as the angle of debonding increases the composite Young's modulus decreases. Further, the Young's modulus at a given angle of debonding increases with the inclusion wall thickness. The rate of decrease of the composite Young's modulus for a given wall thickness is not linear with respect to the extent of debonding. More specifically, the Young's modulus tends to slowly decrease as the debonding is formed and its rate of decrease rapidly grows as the extent of debonding passes approximately 20° . As the angle of debonding increases above approximately 50° the Young's modulus become approximately constant and exhibit a final drop close to 90° , which represents the case of a fully removed inclusion. This trend is made clearer by the strain energy release rate in Figure 3b which shows that the debonding condition becomes unstable for a debonding angle approximately equal to 20° . Figure 4(b) shows a shift in the critical value of strain energy release rate towards higher debonding angles as the radius ratio increases. The decrease in the strain energy release rate after reaching a peak values implies that no additional effort is required for debond propagation along the interface.

Figure 4(a). Relative change in the effective Young's modulus per unit inclusion volume fraction and (b) strain energy release rate as a function of the debonding angle.

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of particle-matrix debonding on the elastic properties of particulate composites has been studied in this paper. A computationally efficient method has been proposed to characterize stress concentration and elastic properties of particulate composites. For the selected system, the critical debonding extent that leads to system instability is found to be approximately 20° . Decreasing the inclusion wall thickness increases the value of the critical debonding angle while increasing the stress concentration at the interface.

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APPENDIX

The deformations of an isotropic and homogenous body in absence of bulk loads are described by the Navier-Cauchy equation

$$(\lambda + \mu)\nabla(\nabla \cdot \vec{u}) + \mu\Delta\vec{u} = \vec{0} \quad (\text{A1})$$

Where λ and μ are the Lamé's constants and \vec{u} is the displacement vector. Referring to the spherical coordinate system in Figure 1b, assuming cylindrical symmetry with respect to the y -direction, and symmetry with respect to the xz -plane, the nonzero components of the displacement and stress fields can be expressed as [18]

$$u_r(r, \theta) = \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^{\infty} [A_n(n+1)(n-2+4\nu)r^{n+1} + nB_n r^{n-1}]P_n(\cos\theta) + \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^{\infty} \left[n \frac{C_n}{r^n} (n+3-4\nu) - \frac{D_n(n+1)}{r^{n+2}} \right] P_n(\cos\theta) \quad (\text{A2a})$$

$$u_\theta(r, \theta) = \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^{\infty} \left[A_n(n+5-4\nu)r^{n+1} + B_n r^{n-1} + \frac{C_n}{r^n} (-n+4-4\nu) + \frac{D_n}{r^{n+2}} \right] \frac{dP_n(\cos\theta)}{d\theta} \quad (\text{A2b})$$

$$\sigma_{rr}(r, \theta) = 2\mu \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^{\infty} [A_n(n+1)(n^2 - n - 2 - 2\nu)r^n + nB_n(n-1)r^{n-2}]P_n(\cos\theta) + 2\mu \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^{\infty} \left[n \frac{C_n}{r^{n+1}} (n^2 + 3n - 2\nu) - \frac{D_n(n+1)(n+2)}{r^{n+3}} \right] P_n(\cos\theta) \quad (\text{A2c})$$

$$\tau_{r\theta}(r, \theta) = 2\mu \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^{\infty} [A_n(n^2 + 2n - 1 + 2\nu)r^n + B_n(n-1)r^{n-2}] \frac{dP_n(\cos\theta)}{d\theta} + 2\mu \sum_{n=0,2,\dots}^{\infty} \left[\frac{C_n}{r^{n+1}} (n^2 - 2 + 2\nu) - \frac{D_n(n+2)}{r^{n+3}} \right] \frac{dP_n(\cos\theta)}{d\theta} \quad (\text{A2d})$$

where A_n , B_n , C_n , and D_n are unknown coefficients, ν is the Poisson's ratio, and $P_n(\cos\theta)$ is the n -th Legendre polynomial. For even indices, the Legendre polynomials and their derivatives are orthogonal with respect to θ in the range $[0, \pi/2]$. In addition,

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} P_n(\cos\theta)P_n(\cos\theta)d\cos\theta = \frac{1}{2n+1} \quad (\text{A3a})$$

$$\int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{dP_n(\cos\theta)}{d\theta} \frac{dP_n(\cos\theta)}{d\theta} d\cos\theta = \frac{n(n+1)}{2n+1} \quad (\text{A3b})$$

REFERENCES

1. Ishai, O., C. Hiel, and M. Luft, *Long-term hygrothermal effects on damage tolerance of hybrid composite sandwich panels*. Composites, 1995. 26(1): 47-55.
2. Tagliavia, G., M. Porfiri, and N. Gupta, *Damping characteristics of glass hollow particle filled vinyl ester matrix composites*. Journal of Composite Materials, 2008. doi: 10.1177/0021998308097683.
3. Gupta, N., E. Woldesenbet, and P. Mensah, *Compression properties of syntactic foams: Effect of cenosphere radius ratio and specimen aspect ratio*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2004. 35(1): 103-111.
4. Porfiri, M. and N. Gupta, *Effect of volume fraction and wall thickness on the elastic properties of hollow particle filled composites*. Composites Part B: Engineering, 2009. doi:10.1016/j.compositesb.2008.09.002 (in press).
5. Bardella, L. and F. Genna, *On the elastic behavior of syntactic foams*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 2001. 38(40-41): 7235-7260.
6. Huang, J.S. and L.J. Gibson, *Elastic moduli of a composite of hollow spheres in a matrix*. Journal of Mechanics and Physics of Solids, 1993. 41(1): 55-75.
7. Pal, R., *New models for effective young's modulus of particulate composites*. Composites Part B: Engineering, 2005. 36(6-7): 513-523.
8. Tagliavia, G., M. Porfiri, and N. Gupta, *Analysis of flexural properties of hollow-particle filled composites*. Composites Part B: Engineering, 2009. doi:10.1016/j.compositesb.2009.03.004
9. Huang, N.C. and M.Y. Korobeinik, *Interfacial debonding of a spherical inclusion embedded in an infinite medium under remote stress*. International Journal of Fracture, 2001. 107(1): 11-30.
10. Rabbani, M., K. Maleknejad, N. Aghazadeh, and R. Mollapourasl, *Computational projection methods for solving Fredholm integral equation*. Applied Mathematics and Computation, 2007. 191(1): 140-143.
11. Babolian, E. and L.M. Delves, *An Augmented Galerkin method for first kind Fredholm equations*. IMA Journal of Applied Mathematics, 1979. 24(2): 157-174.
12. Willis, J.R., *The Penny-shaped crack on an interface*. *The Quarterly Journal of Mechanics and Applied Mathematics*, 1972. 25(3): 367-385.
13. Teng, H., *Effective longitudinal shear modulus of a unidirectional fiber composite containing interfacial cracks*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 1992. 29(12): 1581-1595.
14. Willis, J.R., *Interfacial Stresses Induced by arbitrary loading of dissimilar elastic half-spaces joined over a circular region*. IMA Journal of Applied Mathematics, 1971. 7(2): 179-197.
15. Altenbach, H., S.A. Smirnov, and V. Kulyk, *Analysis of a spherical crack on the interface of a two-phase composite*. Mechanics of Composite Materials, 1995. 31(1): 11-19.
16. Martynenko, M. and I. Lebedyeva, *Axisymmetric problem for a spherical crack on the interface of elastic media*. Journal of Engineering Mathematics, 2006. 56(4): 371-384.
17. Christensen, R.M., *Mechanics of Composite Materials*. 1979, Mineola, NY: Dover.
18. Lure, A.I., *Three-Dimensional Problems of the Theory of Elasticity*. 1964, New York: Interscience Publishers.